

been identified four prominent genetic subtypes in DLBCL, termed MCD (based on the co-occurrence of MYD88L265P and CD79B mutations), BN2 (based on BCL6 fusions and NOTCH2 mutations), N1 (based on NOTCH1 mutations), and EZB (based on EZH2 mutations and BCL2 translocations). Genetic aberrations in multiple genes distinguished each genetic subtype from other DLBCLs [5].

Age, IPI, and the viability of dose-intensified techniques should all be considered when stratifying treatment regimens. When possible, enrollment in a clinical trial is suggested. Precautions such as the injection of prednisone for many days as 'prephase' treatment are recommended in instances with a large tumor load to avoid tumor lysis syndrome. Avoid dose decreases due to haematological toxicity. Febrile neutropaenia warrants the use of haematopoietic growth agents on a preventive basis in patients treated with curative aim and those over the age of 60 years [6, 7]. As such, various biomarkers are required for prognostic evaluation and to identify individuals at the highest risk to aim for individualized therapeutic options [8].

References

1. Swerdlow SH, Campo E, Harris NL, Jaffe ES, Pileri SA, Thiele J. WHO classification of tumors of the haematopoietic and lymphoid tissues. Lyon, France: *International Agency for Research on Cancer*, 2017.

2. Laurie H. Sehn, and Gilles Salles. Diffuse Large B-Cell Lymphoma. *N Engl J Med* 2021; 384:842.

3. Harris NL, Jaffe ES, Stein H, et al. A revised EuropeaneAmerican classification of lymphoid neoplasms: a proposal from the International Lymphoma Study Group. *Blood* 1994; 84: 1361e92.

4. International Non-Hodgkin's Lymphoma Prognostic Factors Project. A predictive model for aggressive non-Hodgkin's lymphoma. *N Engl J Med*. 1993 Sep 30;329(14):987-94. doi: 10.1056/NEJM199309303291402. PMID: 8141877.

5. Roland Schmitz, Ph.D., George W. Wright, Ph.D. et al. Genetics and Pathogenesis of Diffuse Large B-Cell Lymphoma. *N Engl J Med* 2018; 378:1396-1407. DOI: 10.1056/NEJMoa1801445. 23

6. Récher C, Coiffier B, Haioun C et al. Intensified chemotherapy with ACVBP plus rituximab versus standard CHOP plus rituximab for the treatment of diffuse large B-cell lymphoma (LNH03-2B): an open-label randomised phase 3 trial. *Lancet* 2011; 378: 1858–1867

7. Reyes F, Lepage E, Ganem G et al. ACVBP versus CHOP plus radiotherapy for localized aggressive lymphoma. *N Engl J Med* 2005; 352: 1197–1205.

8. Alizadeh AA, Eisen MB, Davis RE et al. Distinct types of diffuse large B-cell lymphoma identified by gene expression profiling. *Nature*. (2000) 403:503–11. doi: 10.1038/35000501.

LONG-TERM RESULTS OF COMPLETE REMOVABLE PROSTHETICS IN PATIENTS OF VARIOUS GROUPS DEPENDING ON AGE AND GEND

Bayramov Y.I.

Doctor of Philosophy in Medicine, assistant Azerbaijan Medical University, Department of Orthopedic Dentistry Baku, Azerbaijan

Mehmani I.H.

Doctor of Philosophy in Medicine, Assistant Azerbaijan Medical University, Department of Orthopedic Dentistry, Baku, Azerbaijan

Mehmani V.R.

Azerbaijan Medical University, Department of Orthopedic Dentistry, assistant Baku, Azerbaijan

Ashrafov D.S.

Azerbaijan Medical University, Department of Orthopedic Dentistry, assistant Baku, Azerbaijan

Abstract

As a result of research, it was found that changes in bone tissue prosthetic bed were most observed in patients aged 60 years and above. There were no significant differences in anatomical and topographic changes, depending on the sex of patients. Research results indicate that atrophic processes in the tissues of the prosthetic bed during the use of complete removable dentures are the most harmful factor significantly worsening the conditions for repeated patient prosthetics. It is necessary to create new structures complete removable dentures, which would reduce the negative impact on tissues of the prosthetic bed to the minimum.

Keywords: complete removable denture, atrophic processes, prosthetic bed tissue.

One of the most complex and urgent problems of modern orthopedic dentistry is a quality rehabilitation of patients with complete adentia [1,2]. This is due to the need to create prostheses, which are optimal in

terms of functional, aesthetic and psychological indicators of treatment outcomes the use of lamellar prostheses occurs abrasion plastic teeth and atrophy of the prosthetic bed [3,5,8]. As a result the height of the lower third, the face decreases, speech, aesthetics are

disturbed, the process of chewing food worsens. Complete absence of teeth dominates in its devastating consequences for the dentoalveolar systems among all dental diseases. Age changes mucosal conditions and the degree of atrophy of the tissues of the prosthetic bed have key to predicting the effectiveness of treatment and are a direct relationship with the duration of positive results of prosthetics.

According to WHO, the complete absence of teeth occurs in 25-40% of people over 55 years [4,7]. According to studies by different authors, in 26-55% of patients atrophy of the alveolar processes of the jaws is pronounced, which in turn, worsens the fixation of complete removable dentures [6] dental implants. We noted that after repeated prosthetics were most often treated by patients of older age groups. Considering the

above, the aim of our study was study of changes in the anatomical and topographic features of tissues prosthetic bed in different age groups in patients using complete removable dentures.

Materials and methods of research.

We examined 120 patients with complete secondary adentia who applied to the clinic for repeated prosthetics. All patients were divided into three age groups: the first 40-54 years old, the second 55-70 years old and the third is over 70 years old. According to statistics, this amounted to – 82 (68.33%) men and 38 (31.67%) women from among those who applied for a second prosthetics. Additionally, factors such as the absence general somatic pathology, absence of inflammatory processes and injuries oral cavity, bad habits.

Table 1

All patients were divided according to the type of bone tissue atrophy of the prosthetic bed in depending on age and gender.

Groups			jaw atrophy by classification						
			to Schroeder			To Keller			
			I	II	III	I	II	III	IV
4054 years -	man	№	4	1	-	7	-	1	-
		%	80%	20%	-	87.5	-	12.5	-
	Woman	№	8	2	-	1		1	1
		%	80%	20%	-	33.33		33.33	33.33
55-70 years	man	№	12	16	3	1	18	2	1
		%	38.7%	51.6	9.7	4.55	81.81	9.09	4.55
	Woman	№	13	23	3	6	24	5	1
		%	33.33%	58.98	7.69	16.66	66.66	13.88	2.77
over 70 years	man	№	1	2	2	2	6	4	2
		%	20%	40%	40%	14.28	42.88	28.57	14.3
	Woman	№	2	20	8	7	22	5	3
		%	6.66	66.66	26.68	18.91	59.48	13.51	8.1
Total	man	№	17	19	5	10	24	7	3
		%	41.46%	46.34%	12.2	22.72	54.54	15.9	6.84
	Woman	№	23	45	11	14	46	11	5
		%	29.11%	56.96	13.93	18.42	60.52	14.49	6.57

To determine the degree of atrophy of the bone tissue of the prosthetic bed used intraoral examination, studied diagnostic models jaws and used scanning and measurement of digital indicators on virtual models. To determine the degree of jaw atrophy used the classification according to Schroeder and Kohler.

Results and its discussion.

The results of the survey show that in 87% of patients with complete absence of teeth in the upper jaw belong to class I and II according to Schroeder classification, which is considered a satisfactory condition for prosthetics. Satisfactory clinical conditions for prosthetics on the lower jaw were found only in 20% of

cases. In 58.3% of individuals, uniform atrophy of the alveolar process was noted, which corresponds to type II according to Koehler. The survey results revealed that the age of patients has a significant impact on the processes of atrophy tissues of the prosthetic bed, namely in II and III age groups.

The condition of the mucosa was assessed according to the Supple classification. Among of the examined patients, predominantly normal compliance of the mucous membrane, which corresponds to class I according to Supple (36.66%). In 32.5% of cases - class II according to Suppli, class III according to Suppli - in 10.0% observations, class IV 20.8%

Table 2

The state of the mucous membrane of the prosthetic bed, depending on age and gender

groups			mucosal classification according to Supple			
			I	II	III	IV
40-54 years	Man	No	3	1	2	-
		%	50	16.67	33.33	
	woman	No	2	1	1	3
		%	28.57	14.29	14.29	42.85
55-70 years	Man	No	13	10	3	3
		%	44.83	34.49	10.34	10.34
	woman	No	22	9	4	8
		%	51.16	20.94	9.3	18.6
over 70 years	Man	No	-	4	1	1
		%		66.67	16.67	16.66
	Woman	No	4	14	1	10
		%	13.8	48.28	3.44	34.48
total	Man	No	16	15	6	4
		%	39.02	36.59	14.64	9.75
	woman	No	28	24	6	21
		%	35.44	30.38	7.6	26.58

The results of the examination that the condition of the oral mucosa practically does not differ by gender. In the age group 70 and there is an increase in patients with the second class of classification mucous membrane.

According to the data obtained, 87% of patients with complete absence of teeth, have satisfactory conditions for the manufacture of complete removable prostheses. At the same time, the favorable clinical situation regarding lower jaw was observed only in 20% of cases. According to examination shows that the atrophy of the tissues of the prosthetic bed is significantly increases in older age groups.

References

1. Alimskij A. V., Vusatj V. S., Prikuls V. F. On the issue of providing orthopedic dental care to elderly people with a complete lack of teeth living in Moscow and Moscow region. *Stomatologija*. 2004;4:72-75
2. Douglass C. W., Shih A., Ostry L. Will there be a need for complete dentures in the United States in 2020. *The Journal of Prosthetic Dentistry*. 2002;87(1):5-8. Надійшла 26.10.1

3. Solov'jov M. M., Jaremenko A. I., Alehova T. M., Raad Z. K. *Dental implantology*. SPb.: Izd-vo SPbGMU; 2008:214.

4. Jerys L. B., Klepach M. M. Improvement of articulation-occlusal relationships in patients with complete loss of teeth. *Ukrai'ns'kyj stomatologichnyj al'manah*. 2012;3:95

5. Kryzhanovs'kyj A. Je. Diagnosis of atrophy of toothless jaws in the dynamics of complete removable prosthetics. *Vseukrai'ns'ka naukovo-praktychna konferencija Zaporizhzhja*; 2015:30-31.

6. Pelehan L. I. Improving the effectiveness of treatment of patients with complete loss of teeth. Abstract of a candidate's thesis of medical sciences. *Ivano-Frankivs'k*; 2003:20.

7. Pysarenko O. A. Clinical and technological aspects of improving the quality of full dentures on the upper jaw. Abstract of a candidate's thesis of medical sciences. *Poltava*; 2001:24.

8. Sadykov M. I. Modern methods of orthopedic treatment and rehabilitation of patients with complete absence of teeth. Abstract of a doctoral thesis of medical sciences. *Samara*; 2002:37